

Family Crises as depicted in the novel *The Promise* by Nikita Singh

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Abstract:

Literature mirrors the society. It reflects all the aspects of human life. It depicts the social, moral, cultural realities and so as the individual's psychological state as well. In all these spheres of human life the family plays an important role. Hence, the depiction of family is observed in Indian English literature as well too. The different facets of family like traditional, united, happy, supportive, caring, educated, modern can be seen in any piece of literature. Alike these all, family crises are also reflected in many more English fictional and non-fictional writings. In literature, family crises are often portrayed to reflect social realities and human struggles within relationships. Contemporary Indian fiction frequently highlights on the themes of emotional conflict, generation gap and the complexities of family expectations.

In the present research paper, the researcher has tried to inspect on the family aspect in the novel *The Promise* by Nikita Singh. The novel, *The Promise* presents the powerful narrative highlighting the emotional crises within family relationships. The present research paper aims to examine those family crises as depicted in the novel and how these crises influence the emotional journeys of the characters in the novel.

Keywords: Family Crises, Depiction, Emotional Conflict, Family Complexities.

Introduction:

Family, the most important social institution plays important role in shaping an individual's identity, emotional stability, and moral values. It provides support, love, and security, but it can also become a source of conflict and emotional struggle. In literature, family relationships often serve as a central theme through which writers explore human emotions, social expectations, and personal conflicts.

In contemporary Indian fiction, many authors focus on the complexities of family relationships and the emotional crises that arise within them. These crises may emerge due to misunderstandings, generation gaps, unrealistic expectations, or lack of communication among family members. Such conflicts not only affect

the relationships within the family but also influence the psychological development of individuals.

Objective of Present Research Study:

Many studies in literature highlight family crises arising due to changes in social structure, difference of thoughts and life style in two generations and changing cultural expectations. In traditional societies, family roles were clearly defined, but modern lifestyles and individual aspirations have created new challenges within family relationships.

Literary critics also emphasize that emotional communication plays an essential role in maintaining healthy family relationships. The lack of communication develops

misunderstandings and emotional distance which further leads to conflict and instability in family.

In the present research paper, researcher has selected the novel *The Promise* by Indian writer, Nikita Singh. She is known for her ability to portray emotional realities and dynamics of relationships. In the selected novel, she has portrayed her characters in such a realistic way that any one as reading it, can feel and experience the pain, loss, disappointment, and confusion due to broken promises as her characters go through. One can easily get related to the experience of her central characters and feel the emotional turmoil felt by Shambhavi Sen, Mr. Sen and Arjun Datta. *The Promise* explores the emotional depth of relationships among these characters and highlights the struggles faced by them when family bonds become complicated. The novel illustrates how family crises can deeply affect the lives of these individuals, shaping their perceptions of trust, love, and responsibility. Through the experiences of these characters, the novel presents a realistic portrayal of modern family dynamics and emphasizes the importance of understanding and emotional support.

The works of Nikita Singh often revolve around themes of relationships, emotional struggles, and personal growth. Her novels typically explore the complexities of love, friendship, and family bonds. Through simple yet emotionally engaging narratives, she portrays the internal struggles of characters who attempt to move through difficult relationships.

Singh's novels are popular mostly among young readers. She writes about love, friendship, relationship, break-up, struggles in life. The researcher feels that the element of family and family crises can also be highlighted in her works. However, the present study is an attempt to flash upon the family crises as observed in *The Promise*.

Observed family crises in the novel *The Promise*:

Conflict between Shambhavi's individual aspirations and family requirements:

Shambhavi Sen, a young girl, central figure in the novel has her own planning in life. One side, she aspires for a beautiful life after getting married to Arjun Datta, whom she loves blindly, trusting fully him and gets pregnant before marriage. She aspires for a happy and loving family. When she discloses her pregnancy to Arjun, he denies to accept Shambhavi and backs his responsibility. Another side she must look after her family requirements. She must look after her father's treatment, arrange money for the medical emergency whenever required. She works very hard even when she herself required rest in her pregnancy. But Shambhavi, keeps her individual needs aside and tries hard to care for her father, Mr. Sen and her unborn baby. "Her hard work had taken a toll on her health. She had grown weaker. She felt guilty about not eating and resting enough, which was causing harm to her baby, but she planned to make it all up with the rest she was going to get in the last two months of her pregnancy She was in the seventh month of her pregnancy and had saved enough to last her through her delivery. But she needed to earn more to take care of her baby and father when she wouldn't be able to get up and work, right after the baby was born." (Singh, 2012, p-139) This illustrates how such family needs can create pressure of responsibility and confusion. Characters may feel obligated to satisfy their families even when it means sacrificing their own comfort, dreams or happiness.

Conflict between Trust and Promises:

Trust plays an important role in family. It plays the role of backbone of family in maintaining strong family relationships. Healthy family relationships are built on trust. In the selected novel, promises symbolize emotional

commitment and responsibility among family members. Shambhavi and Arjun promised each other to live entire life with each other and never get separated. But Arjun's past experience, enforced him to humiliate Shambhavi. Arjun questions, "Whose baby it is? ANSWER ME! Don't act so innocent, okay? The show is over. I know this was a set up. Now just tell me what you want and get lost." (Singh, 2012, p -110) Arjun blames her with prejudice and runs away from her leaving her alone in such a state when she was needing him the most. Arjun's past experience causes to create struggle between the relationship of Shambhavi and Arjun and spoil their present. Shambhavi replies, "If that is really what you think, I think you should leave, get out, ARJUN DATTA, DON'T MAKE ME SAY THAT AGAIN. GET THE HELL OUT OF HERE. YOU DON'T KNOW SHIT ABOUT WHAT I WANT AND WHAT I DON'T. SO, DO NOT MAKE ASSUMPTIONS" (Singh, 2012, p -112). When promises are broken, it creates feelings of betrayal and disappointment. The emotional impact of such betrayal is deeply felt by the characters, leading to mistrust and resentment.

Emotional Conflict within the Family:

One of the most prominent aspects of family crisis depicted in the novel is emotional misunderstanding among family members. Emotional conflict often arises when individuals fail to express their true feelings or when their emotions are ignored by others. This element can be observed through the Shambhavi and Arjun's character. After the breakup, none of them take initiative to bridge the relation with communication. Arjun sends a blank cheque signed by him to Shambhavi by the hands of his assistant-cum-driver, Faisal, with his biased judgement about Shambhavi's pregnancy as fake just to trap him to get his name and fame, money and wealth. On the other hand, Shambhavi is

straight, practical. She is honest. Her love is pure for Arjun. She loved him not his money. Hence, she denied to accept the cheque sent by Arjun. What we explore here, is that both of them never tries to communicate each other. Both misunderstand each other which leads to their emotional conflict. "What I don't understand is that- if all you needed was my money, why did you need to drag a baby into this? Don't you have a heart? What does an innocent child have to do with this?" (Singh, 2012, p -110). Being self-cautious, Shambhavi answers, "I need money, yes, but I earn my own bread, Mr. Datta. I do it by my own competence. You might have a lot of dough, but I do not need a man to provide for me" ((Singh, 2012, p -111).

Psychological Effects of Family Crises:

Family crises do not only affect relationships but also affect the mental and emotional well-being of individuals. Shambhavi, in need of money for her father's operation, arranges her most favorite painting's exhibition for sale. Her most favourite painting is purchased by her **gynecologist**. She is attached utmost with her favourite and loving paintings. She misses them. The wheelchair accident taken place on staircase with her father in which Mr. Sen expires. Shambhavi loses her baby while trying to hold tightly the wheelchair to save her father from mishap about to take place. But she fails and along with wheelchair she gets stumbled over staircase and lose her baby too. Her attempt to save her father turned useless losing her baby, Pari. This incident disrupted Shambhavi's mental balance. She lost her consciousness. "DON'T TOUCH ME! Stay away. AWAY, she yelled. "LET ME GO! STOP IT! DON'T YOU SEE? MY BABY NEEDS ME! Please let me go to my baby.... I want to see her... She is my only family...." (Singh, 2012, p -165) These psychological struggles highlight how deeply family relationships affect personal identity and

emotional stability. When individuals feel unsupported or misunderstood by their families, they may experience feelings of isolation and insecurity.

Personal Growth and Transformation:

Bot, Shambhavi and Arjun, begin to understand that relationships require patience, understanding, and emotional honesty. They realize their mistakes of blaming each other. Both loves each other utmost. They have concern for each other. So, Shambhavi called him once keeping aside all the things. Arjun, too was informed by Faizal and Mili, Shambhavi's friend, the hard time and condition faced by Shambhavi. Faizal told Arjun about rejection of blank cheque offered by him to Shambhavi. Finally, Arjun understands Shambhavi and his love for her. Arjun regrets a lot for losing their baby. He helps and supports Shambhavi to come out from the shock she received after the death of her father and their baby, Pari. He avails all the medicare to Shambhavi and pays the hospital and medical bills as well. Through their experiences, both of them gradually learn important lessons about forgiveness, empathy, and communication. Despite the emotional pain caused by family conflicts, the novel ultimately suggests that crises can lead to personal growth and self-discovery. This transformation highlights the possibility of

healing and reconciliation even after family conflicts. By acknowledging their mistakes and expressing their true feelings, the characters move toward rebuilding their relationships.

Conclusion:

The novel *The Promise* by Nikita Singh presents a thoughtful exploration of family crises and their impact on individuals. Through the depiction of emotional misunderstandings, broken promises, and conflicting expectations, the novel illustrates the complex nature of family relationships. The portrayal of family crises in the novel reflects broader social realities and highlights the challenges faced by modern families. By addressing these issues, the novel encourages readers to value communication, understanding, and emotional support within family relationships.

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